

PROPOSAL FOR A PROTOCOL FOR ADAPTATION OF THE ORAL ENVIRONMENT PRIOR TO MAJOR SURGERY: A SERIES OF CASES.

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ABSTRACT

The intensive involvement of the dentistry team as a multidisciplinary strategy in the preoperative period showed an accelerated recovery of patients undergoing oncological surgery. Protocols were adopted that included oral preparation before surgery, which brought good results in the postoperative period for these patients. However, perioperative oral practices as a protective factor have not yet been well understood and need to be further studied. OBJECTIVE: to present a medical-surgical care protocol for patients, with adaptation of the oral environment prior to major orthopedic surgeries, specifically hip arthroplasty, in a university hospital. SAMPLE: 23 patients who underwent an outpatient consultation

with the orthopedic surgeon and were referred to the hospital's dentistry service to adapt the oral environment prior to hip arthroplasty surgery.

MATERIAL AND METHOD: Case series study in which the hospital records of 23 patients were evaluated to investigate the main postoperative complications found in a group where 100% of patients underwent previous mouth preparation. For this purpose, dental records were collected with patient data such as the patient's medical record number, odontogram and report on the execution of the dental procedures performed. Two years after the adoption of this system, the patients' medical records were coded and analyzed by a researcher who, using the hospital's computer system, verified the length of stay for each patient, the execution of the procedure in the surgical center and the main reports of complications in each patient. patient such as postoperative infection, pneumonia, admission to an intensive care unit as well as the hospital discharge report. **RESULTS:** We observed that 100% of patients who underwent previous mouth preparation, none contracted pneumonia; There were no reports of dental loss or trauma during intubation or throughout the hospitalization period; The average length of stay was 9 days; There was one admission to the intensive care unit with a history of sepsis, cardiac arrest and subsequent death; Among the most reported postoperative complications, in addition to pain, we found volunteers with infection at the surgical site and two volunteers with deep vein thrombosis; 15 volunteers were discharged from hospital.

Keywords: perioperative management, dental, oral management.

INTRODUCTION

The intensive involvement of the dentistry team as a multidisciplinary strategy in the preoperative period showed an accelerated recovery of patients undergoing oncological surgery. Protocols were adopted that included oral preparation before surgery, which brought good results in the postoperative period for these patients.¹

Perioperative oral management is widely recognized in Japan's healthcare system. Conventionally, the surgeon refers patients with oral problems to a dental or oral surgery clinic in the hospital. The effectiveness of introducing this system was demonstrated in 7715 patients undergoing oncological surgery. A 20% oral intervention rate significantly reduced the incidence of postoperative pneumonia and indicated that this system could be very useful in surgical patients.^{2,3}

For positive neurosurgical results a multidisciplinary team consisting of anesthesiologists, dentists/hygienists/dental technicians, nurses, physiotherapists, pharmacists, and nutritionists was organized and this system decreased the duration of admission to surgery, and was found useful in providing discharge medical care.²

Oral diseases prior to a hospital medical-surgical procedure are a risk factor for the development of postoperative complications. However, perioperative oral practices as a protective factor have not yet been well understood and need to be further studied.⁴

OBJECTIVE

This work aims to show a medical-surgical care protocol for patients, with adaptation of the oral environment prior to major orthopedic surgeries, specifically hip arthroplasty, in a university hospital.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Study was approved by the HUUFMA CEP under number 23178719.2.0000.5086. The volunteers signed the free and informed consent form.

SAMPLE

The sample consists of 23 patients who underwent an outpatient consultation with the orthopedic surgeon and were referred to the hospital's dentistry service to adapt their oral environment prior to hip arthroplasty surgery. The oral adjustment carried out consisted of basically 4 steps:⁵

1. Supra-gingival and sub-gingival scaling improve gingivitis and periodontitis
2. Extraction of condemned teeth
3. Restoration of caries cavities with composite resin
4. Guidance and oral hygiene and flossing

After the dental treatment, the patients were called for the elective medical-surgical procedure. Of these 23 patients, 7 were excluded for not having undergone the medical procedure, leaving 16 volunteers in the sample.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Case series study in which the hospital records of 23 patients were evaluated to investigate the main postoperative complications found in a group where 100% of patients underwent previous mouth preparation. For this purpose, dental records were collected with patient data such as the patient's medical record number, odontogram and report on the execution of the dental procedures performed.

Two years after the adoption of this system, the patients' medical records were coded and analyzed by a researcher who, using the hospital's computer system, verified the length of stay for each patient, the execution of the procedure in the surgical center and the main reports of complications in each patient. patient such as postoperative infection, pneumonia, admission to an intensive care unit as well as the hospital discharge report.

RESULTS

The results found were:

PATI ENT	DAY S	INFE CTIO N	INTE NSIV E CAR E	DISC HAR GE	PNE UMO NIA	SEP SIS	CAR DIAC ARR EST	HAV EN'T HAD SUR GER Y YET	OTH ERS
Case 1	2	No	No	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 2	2	No	No	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 3								yes	
Case 4	3	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 5								Yes	
Case 6	24	yes	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 7								Yes	
Case 8	40	yes	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 9	9	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 10	3	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		

Case 11	2	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 12								Yes	
Case 13	3	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 14	3	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 15	10	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		Hiv, deep vein thro mbo sis
Case 16	3	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		
Case 17								Yes	
Case 18								Yes	
Case 19	23	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		deep vein thro mbo sis
Case 20	4	No	no	Yes	No	no	No		

Case 21	10	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes		death
Case 22								Yes	
Case 23	3	No	no	Yes	No	No	No		

We observed in the table above that of the 100% of patients who underwent previous mouth preparation, none contracted pneumonia; There were no reports of tooth loss during intubation, extubation or throughout the hospitalization period; The average length of stay was nine days; There was one admission to the intensive care unit with a history of sepsis, cardiac arrest and subsequent death; Among the most reported postoperative complications, in addition to pain, we found volunteers with infection at the surgical site and two volunteers with deep vein thrombosis; Fifteen volunteers were discharged from hospital;

DISCUSSION:

Some protocols have been reported in the literature such as ERAS in which protocol items are developed and executed by a team of professionals, including surgeons, anesthesiologists, nurses, nutritionists, physiotherapists and others, and together they maintain control over the entire patient journey. patient and continually audit treatment. ^{1,2}

Studies that can provide a high level of evidence, such as randomized controlled clinical trials, are difficult to carry out because the dental intervention must have a benefit, and the negative control, which would have no dental intervention, could not be established from an ethical point of view. Therefore, well-designed multicenter studies to evaluate

relationships between the degree of dental intervention and perioperative benefits and outcomes are essential.

Currently, the contribution to general health through the maintenance of oral health is a significant topic in dentistry, as an example we have the effects of periodontal treatment on the metabolic control of diabetes, which has been studied extensively.^{6,7}

We found that the barrier between the dental team and the medical team is beginning to disappear in the field of perioperative management, allowing for better medical treatment such as the PERIO protocol widely developed in Japan.^{1,2,3}

CONCLUSION

More multicenter studies should be carried out with all types of patients from all surgical specialties to verify the real effectiveness of mouth preparation prior to major surgery.

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